

A Versatile Colorimetric Probe based on Thiosemicarbazide-Amine Proton Transfer

Céline Calvino, Marek Piechowicz, Stuart J. Rowan, Stephen Schrettl, Christoph Weder*

Abstract: There is significant interest in the rapid and efficient detection of amines, which are widely used in different industries and also serve as markers in many biological processes. We show here that the coupling of a thiosemicarbazide binding motif and a naphthalimide-based chromophore affords highly sensitive sensor molecules, which can indicate the presence of amines with a pronounced and readily visible color change. We demonstrate that the binding mechanism involves a proton transfer from the thiosemicarbazide to the analyte. This process renders the mechanism highly sensitive and broadly exploitable. The potential usefulness of the sensor is demonstrated by fabricating an indicator paper, which allows the detection of volatile amines at concentrations as low as ca. 10 ppm.

Sensor molecules which change their optical properties upon exposure to alcohols, thiols, organophosphates, amines, ions, and other chemical species are attracting widespread interest.^{[1],[2],[3],[4],[5],[6]} While fluorescent sensor molecules require excitation with UV light to allow for a read-out,^{[7],[8],[9],[10]} a similar stimulation is not needed if the sensor changes its absorption characteristics.^{[11],[12],[13]} Such chromogenic sensors can be accessed by covalently linking a chromophore with a binding motif so that the coordination of an analyte to the latter causes a color change and elicits a visually detectable signal.^{[11],[13],[14],[15]} This *binding site-signaling site* colorimetric sensing concept has been extensively studied in the context of anion recognition, using urea-,^[16] thiourea-,^[17] amide-,^[18] or pyrrole-based^{[19],[20]} binding motifs. Thiourea derivatives display a higher acidity ($pK_a(\text{DMSO}) = 21.1$) than ureas ($pK_a(\text{DMSO}) = 26.9$),^[21] which translates into more stable coordination complexes with anions to the extent that deprotonation of the binding site becomes dominant with basic anions.^[22] Thiourea-, thiosemicarbazone-, and thiosemicarbazide-based receptors have been conjugated with different chromophores to create color-changing sensor molecules. The thiosemicarbazide motif, which is particularly attractive due to its biocompatibility,^{[23],[24],[25]} has been conjugated with naphthalimide to afford sensor molecules that form hydrogen-bonded assemblies with anions or are deprotonated by strongly basic anions, leading to a readily detectable color change in the presence of anions.^{[26],[27],[28],[29]} Here, we report that similar species permit the detection of

amines and demonstrate that the binding mechanism involves a proton transfer from the thiosemicarbazide to the analyte.

There is particular interest in the rapid detection of amines, which are widely used in the pharmaceutical, cosmetics, and agrochemical industries.^[30] Aniline/*o*-toluidine and dimethylamine/trimethylamine are biomarkers for lung cancer and uremia, respectively;^[31] aromatic amine derivatives exhibit a high toxicity;^{[32],[33]} and amines and their degradation products can persist in soil, wastewater, or the atmosphere with significant environmental impact on terrestrial and aquatic systems.^{[34],[35]} The thiosemicarbazide-naphthalimide-based chromophore reported here is capable of detecting any of the above species, as well as other analytes with a pK_a value of >9 , it can be embedded in a solid support,^[36] and provides an instantaneous and readily detectable response.

Figure 1. A) Molecular structure of the thiosemicarbazide-naphthalimide-based chromophore **1**. B) UV-Vis absorption spectra of chromophore **1** in DMSO ($c = 0.076 \text{ mmol L}^{-1}$, orange line) and upon titration with aliquots of *n*-butylamine (purple lines). C) Absorption at $\lambda = 574 \text{ nm}$ of the spectra shown in (B) as a function of the molar equivalents of *n*-butylamine added. D) Pictures showing a solution of chromophore **1** in DMSO ($c = 0.076 \text{ mmol L}^{-1}$) upon addition of *n*-butylamine.

The crystalline, yellow thiosemicarbazide-naphthalimide-based chromophore **1** (Figure 1A) was synthesized by modifying a procedure reported by Gunnlaugsson and coworkers and isolated in satisfactory yields (Figure S1,S2).^[37] Solutions of **1** in dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) are yellow and the UV-Vis absorption spectrum shows a narrow absorption band with a maximum (λ_{max}) at 416 nm and a weak shoulder around 574 nm. Upon addition of *n*-butylamine the band centered at 416 nm gradually disappears, whereas the band around 574 nm grows concomitantly and two isosbestic points at 375 and 465 nm can be observed (Figure 1B). A plot of the intensity of the band at 574 nm against the amount of added *n*-butylamine reveals that the conversion is complete at an equimolar ratio of **1** and the amine (Figure 1C). The observed spectral changes indicate the

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formation of a new, well-defined species upon exposing **1** to *n*-butylamine. The corresponding color change from yellow to blue can be readily discerned upon addition of ~0.2 equivalents or ~6 ppm of *n*-butylamine (Figure 1D).

DMSO solutions of **1** were also titrated with diethylamine and triethylamine to determine the response to secondary and tertiary amines; in both cases, the UV-Vis absorption spectra mirror those acquired upon addition of *n*-butylamine (Figure S3), indicating the formation of similar complexes. In the case of diethylamine, full conversion was observed at 1 eq. of the amine, whereas the absorption spectra did not cease to change even after addition of up to 5 eq. of triethylamine (Figure S3). In the case of the latter, a plot of the intensity of the band at 574 nm against the amount of added triethylamine suggests that the corresponding complex is also formed in an equimolar ratio of **1** and the amine (Figure S3D). The observed difference seems to be related to the pK_a values (in DMSO) of the conjugate acids of *n*-butylamine (11.15), diethylamine (10.15), and triethylamine (9.07),^{[38],[39]} suggesting that the mechanism might involve a proton transfer and that the conversion is buffered in the case of triethylamine. Indeed, the absorption changes elicited upon addition of the alkylamines can be completely reversed upon addition of 1 eq. of trifluoroacetic acid (Figure S4), i.e., **1** is fully recovered upon protonating the amine.

The interaction of **1** and *n*-butylamine was further investigated by ^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectroscopy, ^1H , ^1H correlation spectroscopy (COSY), ^1H , ^{13}C and ^1H , ^{15}N heteronuclear single quantum coherence (HSQC) spectroscopy, and ^1H , ^{13}C heteronuclear multiple-bond correlation (HMBC) spectroscopy in DMSO- d_6 . The ^1H NMR spectra of **1** show that the two protons of the thiourea fragment (**a** and **b**) give rise to overlapping single resonances at 10.09 ppm, while the hydrazine NH signal (**c**)

appears at a chemical shift of 9.85 ppm (Figure 2A). This assignment is based on the analysis of the HMBC spectrum of **1**, which reveals long-range couplings of **a** with the phenyl carbons resonating at 126.0 ppm, of **b** with the thiourea carbon resonance at 181.3 ppm, and of **c** with the naphthalimide carbons resonating at 149.8 and 105.4 ppm (Figure S6). Consistently, the ^1H , ^{15}N HSQC spectrum shows couplings of **a**, **b**, and **c** with the corresponding nitrogen atoms resonating at 127.1, 122.7, and 105.7 ppm, respectively (Figure S9).

The ^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra of the equimolar complex of **1** and *n*-butylamine (subsequently referred to as **2**) show a shift of the naphthalimide and aryl resonances (Figure 2A), which can be assigned based on the corresponding 2D NMR spectra (Figure S7). In contrast to the spectra of **1**, the NH proton signals of the thiosemicarbazide moiety could not be unambiguously identified. Only two singlets at 11.16 and 8.13 ppm are observed that each integrate to a single proton, neither of which shows coupling with carbon resonances in the ^1H , ^{13}C HSQC or HMBC spectra (Figure S7), indicating that they could correspond to NH proton resonances. Indeed, the ^1H , ^{15}N HSQC spectrum reveals a single coupling of the signal at 8.13 ppm with a nitrogen resonance at 120.9 ppm, whereas the broad signal at 11.16 ppm does not exhibit any cross-coupling (Figure S5). These findings suggest that the thiosemicarbazide moiety of **2** carries only two protons, corroborating a proton transfer. The lack of cross-coupling and the broad nature of the signal at 11.16 ppm are consistent with a rapid exchange process of the remaining NH proton in solution. The downfield shift of the proton resonance of the *n*-butylamine CH_2 group neighboring the amine suggests the formation of an *n*-butylammonium ion and supports this interpretation (Figure 2A). Similar results were obtained for the diethylamine and triethylamine complexes of **1** (Supporting Information). NMR spectra recorded upon addition

Figure 2. A) Comparison of the ^1H NMR spectra (400 MHz, 297.2 K, DMSO- d_6) of chromophore **1** and an equimolar complex with *n*-butylamine (**2**) formed by proton transfer from the chromophore to the amine ($c = 0.017 \text{ mol L}^{-1}$). B) ^1H , ^{13}C HMBC NMR spectrum of **3** (400 MHz, 297.2 K, DMSO- d_6 , $c = 0.017 \text{ mol L}^{-1}$) formed by deprotonation of the chromophore with potassium *tert*-butoxide.

of an equimolar amount of TFA to **2** show that the original resonances of **1** are recovered and confirm that the deprotonation can be reversed (Figure S10).

In an attempt to restrict the exchange process and determine the site of deprotonation, the potassium complex **3** was prepared by deprotonation of chromophore **1** with an equimolar amount of potassium *tert*-butoxide (Supporting Information). The ^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra of **3** display very similar resonances and chemical shifts as **2** (Figure S5, Supporting Information). However, the two proton resonances at 11.18 and 8.13 ppm, which each show a cross-coupling with a nitrogen resonance in the $^1\text{H},^{15}\text{N}$ HSQC spectrum (Figure S9), now also display couplings with carbon signals in the $^1\text{H},^{13}\text{C}$ HMBC spectrum of **3** (Figure 2B). Thus, the spectrum reveals cross-couplings between the proton signal at 8.13 ppm and the carbon signal 166.7, 143.1, and 118.1 ppm, which correspond to the carbon resonances of the thiourea moiety and the aryl ring (Figure 2B). Additionally, the proton resonance at 11.18 ppm shows cross-couplings with the carbon resonances at 166.7, 144.8, 119.0, and 104.6 ppm of the thiourea moiety and three resonances of the naphthalimide moiety, respectively. These findings suggest that the signal at 11.18 ppm can be assigned to the NH proton **c** neighboring the naphthalimide, whereas the signal at 8.13 ppm corresponds to the NH proton **a** next to the aryl ring. Accordingly, deprotonation with potassium *tert*-butoxide appears to occur in position **b** (Figure 2B), which, by extension, is presumably also the site of deprotonation in the case of the complex formation with amines.

To demonstrate the usefulness of chromophore **1** for the detection of amine vapors, an indicator paper was fabricated by imbibing a cellulose substrate with an acetone solution of **1** (10 mM) and drying in vacuum. Exposure of this indicator to vapors of *n*-butylamine, diethylamine, or triethylamine caused an instantaneous (~2 sec) color change from bright yellow to purple (Figure 3A). The corresponding absorption spectra, which were converted from the measured reflectance spectra before and after exposure, confirm the visual observations and the intensity of the colorimetric response appears to be related to the vapor pressures of the respective amines (Figure 3B). The sensitivity of the system was investigated by exposing the indicator in a closed system to the vapors emanating from aqueous *n*-butylamine solutions, whose concentrations were chosen to establish equilibrium concentrations of 3–250 ppm of amine in the gas phase (Supporting Information). The indicator paper was placed into containers with the different solutions/amine vapor concentrations for 10 min. A plot of the ratio of the absorbances at 550 nm and 413 nm (A_{550}/A_{413}), associated with the deprotonated and protonated forms of **1**, against the amine vapor concentration displays a significant increase between 8 and 30 ppm (Figure 3C). The corresponding photographs of the indicator paper show a clearly discernible color change at an amine content of 8 ppm (Figure 3D), which puts the detection limit to below 10 ppm. The experiment was repeated, but the amine concentration in the aqueous solution was kept constant (80 mM, corresponding to an equilibrium vapor concentration of ~200 ppm) and the exposure time was varied. A plot of A_{550}/A_{413} against the exposure time shows that the colorimetric response

is already discernible within 1 min, continues to increase, and reaches a maximum after 8 min (Figure S12). However, when the accumulated vapor in the headspace of an equilibrated *n*-butylamine solution of the same concentration was collected and actively pumped through the indicator, the purple coloration and spectroscopic response was instantaneous, indicating that the response time not only depends on the amine concentration, but also the gas circulation (Figure S14).

The regeneration of the chromophore and the potential for a repeated colorimetric response was explored in a closed system by consecutively exposing the indicator paper for 10 min to the vapors emanating from an aqueous solution of *n*-butylamine (80 mM) and subsequently for 30 sec to neat trifluoroacetic acid; this cycle was repeated several times. The inspection of A_{550}/A_{413} and the corresponding pictures (Figure 3D) clearly show that the deprotonation and protonation process can be repeated for at least six cycles.

Figure 3. Response of a cellulose-based indicator paper imbibed with chromophore **1**. **A**) Photographs and **(B)** absorption spectra before and after exposure to amine vapors for 3 seconds. **(C)** Plot of the ratio of the absorbance at 550 nm and 413 nm (A_{550}/A_{413}), associated with the deprotonated and the protonated form of **1** of the indicator paper against the *n*-butylamine vapor concentration to which it was exposed for 10 min in a closed system. **(D)** Photographs showing the color of the indicators used in **(C)**. **(E)** Plot of A_{550}/A_{413} and pictures of the indicator paper after repeated exposure to vapors emanating from an aqueous *n*-butylamine solution (80 mM in water; 10 min, top, blue) and trifluoroacetic acid (neat; 30 sec, bottom, yellow). **(F)** Picture demonstrating the capability to detect volatiles generated by rotting salmon. All absorbances A were calculated from the measured reflectances R using $A = \log(1/R)$.

To further expand the scope and demonstrate the versatility of this sensor system, measurements were also carried out with ammonia, pyridine, and different alkyl amines (Figure S11). As expected, the intensity of the colorimetric response increases with the vapor pressure of the respective amine, with more volatile compounds showing the more intense response. Moreover, similar results were obtained when *n*-hexane, ethyl acetate, tetrahydrofuran, acetonitrile, methanol, and ethanol were used as solvent for the amines (Figure S11). Finally, the practical usefulness of the new amine sensing system was demonstrated by the detection of the spoilage of fish. Thus,

container and stored under ambient conditions for one week. When the indicator paper imbibed with **1** was placed inside the container, a visual color change from yellow to purple could be observed (Figure 3F), indicating spoilage and the presence of biogenic volatile amines such as ammonia or trimethylamine that are typically generated by microbial growth during rotting processes.^[40]

In summary, a naphthalimide-thiosemicarbazide based chromophore was shown to be useful for the visible detection of different types of amines via complex formation based on a proton transfer. The process is highly sensitive, and attractive for the integration of optical sensors into solid supports, which offer a convenient way to detect amines with thin films and fibers. The potential usefulness of such sensor molecules was demonstrated by fabricating a solid-state sensor and monitoring the decomposition of fish.

Experimental Section

Supporting Information is available and include Supplementary Figures S1–S15 as well as a comprehensive account of all experimental details, synthetic procedures, analytical data, and NMR spectra of all compounds.

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Entry for the Table of Contents

COMMUNICATION

Efficiently sensing amines is achieved by employing coupling a thiosemicarbazide binding motif to a naphthalimide-based chromophore. A pronounced visible color change indicates the presence of amines. Volatile amines can be detected at concentrations as low as 10 ppm in a process that involves a proton transfer from the thiosemicarbazide.

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